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Parental Participation, A Panacea for Improving Academic Performance Among Secondary School Students in Rivers State

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ABSTRACT

Globally, parents remains the major key factor on which students' education strives, considering the fact that they are the first to set students foundation and perhaps play active role in instructional matters, predominantly in the home and also in school, or in any programme settings. To this end, this study examined parental participation in the academic performance of secondary schools students in Rivers State. The study holistically explores concepts of parental participation, academic performance, why parental participation, its benefits and importance and parental participation as a panacea for students' academic performance among others. The study concludes that parental participation has a significant effect on students' performance, and suggested that parents should as a matter of urgency embark on intensive monitoring as well as evaluation of student's performance to ascertain their study outcomes. Also suggested were provision of pleasant study environment, participation in extra-academic programmes, sound parent/teachers communication network and motivation bid for students' performance.

Keywords: Academic Performance, Panacea, Parental Participation, Students'.

INTRODUCTION

Parental participation in students' academic performance has attracted many educators and researchers in the field of education in the world. Parental participation was identified as a compensation programme among other educational programmes to engage the low income parents to ready their children for better schools and to avoid education loss of the children who are vulnerable (Bakker, Denessen & Brus-Laeven, 2007). Involvement of parents in the education of their school children increase commitment and interest (WEFC, 2000). Thus, it is recommended that educational administrators should address all the challenges that are seen to affect parental participation especially in Senior secondary schools where students' academic performance is currently poor. According to the United Nations Educational, Scientific, and Cultural Organisation (UNESCO, 2003), the argument has a lot of merit in highlighting the importance of parents in their children's education and calling for policies that address barriers that prevent parents from keeping an eye on their children's education in senior secondary schools. This is in favour of the education for all (EFA) movement.

As for some African countries, Parental participation in education has also received the attention of many scholars in connection with students' academic achievement. Eze (2002) has shown that parents are the children's first teachers at home, that parental involvement in their children's study programs improves good performance, and that parents who become more involved in their children's academic activities can help their children acquire early literacy skills for higher academic progress and a positive attitude towards learning (Ndebele, 2015). Nigerian education policies and programs recognise the role of parents in education by implementing decentralisation, which allows parents to

be involved in their children's education. Additionally, they have noted that parents are not doing enough to satisfy their responsibilities, which include paying school fees, attending parent-teacher conferences, and contacting the school about their child's attendance and performance. This goes against the goals of these regulations. According to UNESCO (2000), and Lareau and Manoz (2012), In his article of 2016, Abdul-El-Fattah points out that Parental participation has been regarded as a tool that can enhance students' academic achievement. Efforts have been made by the states and federal governments of Nigeria in regard to programs, policies and practices in the form of parent teacher associations (PTA), School Based Management Committees (SBMCs); and the Whole School Development Planning (WSDP) in promoting strong parents school relationships. According to Abdul-El-Fattah, PTA is a tool of community involvement in education. These programmes were to afford parents, guardians, sponsors and teachers in primary, secondary and tertiary institutions an opportunity to meet, deliberate, analyze issues and follow up on decisions made regarding matters of concern in Nigerian education with the relevant authorities.

But the incidence of academic performance does not appear to be rare in the Nigerian public schools. Adamawa State has experienced poor academic performance among senior secondary school students, prompting ongoing efforts to address the issue. Key factors contributing to this poor performance include limited parental involvement and unfavorable home environments. Issues such as low family income, parents' low educational levels, and other family challenges, including students' school-related activities, are believed to impact academic outcomes. Additionally, in Mubi-North, where most public and private senior secondary schools operate as day schools, parental participation remains low due to economic engagements. Besides, are the perceived thought of delay and waste of time by parents on school meetings and activities that are not necessary, poor parents and teachers' relationship, untimely information regarding educational activities among others, also have adverse effect on not only students' academic performance, but students' attitude and behaviour and even that of teachers. Probable, the combination of these challenges can lead to poor academic performance, depression and misconduct among students (Okwakpan and Okwakpan 2012).

Academic performance represents the outcome of the educational process, reflecting the extent to which students, teachers, or institutions meet educational objectives (Obochi, 2019). It is typically evaluated through examinations or continuous assessments; however, there is no universal agreement on the most effective method of assessment or the relative importance of procedural knowledge (skills) versus declarative knowledge (facts) (Raymond & Afua, 2016; Santovena Casal, 2019; Stacy, 2018; Tarek & Yasmini, 2015). Academic performance serves as an indicator of an individual's standing within an educational institution and as a pathway to employment opportunities. Furthermore, a nation's social and economic development heavily relies on the academic achievements of its students. Of course, academic achievement is an effective tool that the prospects, potential and potential of a student can significantly affect the development of society, especially in the future (Jibrin & Adamu, 2019). Improving students' academic performance therefore, lies not only in the hands of students, but major education stakeholders particularly parents who influence students by shaping their creativity and critical thinking skills, behaviour and attitude towards school (Wang, 2011). Thus, this study aimed to investigate the potential of parental involvement as a magic bullet for raising academic achievement among Rivers State secondary school pupils.

Parental Participation

Parental participation is synonymously used along with involvement. There seems to be that parental participation is a recent field in the education research and has no precise definition. What seems to be are thoughts and perception of perceived viewers and how it's being used in the context of study. Generally speaking, parental engagement refers to the actions parents do at home and at school in order to aid in their kids' academic development. The frequency and quality of communication with teachers, as well as involvement in school events and activities, are frequently used as indicators of parental involvement. Numerous studies have described parental engagement as including a wide range of behaviours and activities at home or at school, such as parental expectations, attitudes, and beliefs about their child's education (Henderson & Mapp 2012).

Parental involvement is framed within Bronfenbrenner's bioecological theory (1979), which highlights the importance of considering both proximal and distal factors—such as socioeconomic

status, ethnic background, and school context—when understanding parental influences on children's cognitive skill development. Studies, including meta-analyses and reviews, have explored the link between early parental involvement and children's academic achievements (Fan & Chen, 2001). Research indicates that both proximal and distal factors influence the extent of parental engagement in literacy activities (Varghese & Wachen, 2016). Despite indirect links between factors like parents' educational attainment, income, and residential status and children's language and literacy development, a strong, direct positive relationship exists between parental involvement and children's cognitive growth (Fan & Chen, 2001). For example, Varghese and Wachen (2016) found that parents' engagement in reading and writing activities, use of advanced language, and responsive parenting significantly and directly enhance children's literacy outcomes.

Academic Performance

To perform is to carry out a complex sequence of steps that combine knowledge and abilities to yield a worthwhile outcome (Elger, 2012). The consequence of education is academic performance, which assesses how successfully a student, instructor, or institution has reached their learning objectives. Lisa (2009) stated that student's performance is very important because it appears to be major criteria by which the effectiveness and success of any educational institutions could be guided. Generally around the world, Traditionally, classroom performance particularly graduation rates and outcomes from standardised tests—was used by educators to gauge student accomplishment (Mugnuson, 2017). Academic performance, according to Obochi (2019), is the capacity to learn and retain information and to express that knowledge orally on writing. To put it another way, students' academic success is determined by how they handle their studies and how well they complete the many assignments that their professors provide them. Academic performance, according to Epunam (2009), is a student's learning results. However, this encompasses the concepts, abilities, and information they have gained from their course both inside and outside of the classroom, which is decided at the conclusion of the session or academic year. It may be poor, good, very good or excellent based on the services put into studies. Okoye and Madueke (2016) observed that the entire school system in Nigeria has in the past and students' extremely poor academic performance in the present has caused widespread worry; the issue is so severe that it has resulted in a decrease in educational standards. To avert this trend, parents among other education stakeholders remains the only pillar on which students can be effectively supervised, monitored, evaluated and perhaps motivated to learn.

Why Parental Participation

Parental participation in a child's education has long been recognized as a significant factor that influences various aspects of a child's holistic development. Delving deep into the nuances of parental involvement reveals multifaceted reasons as to why this form of engagement is crucial, both for students and the broader educational community. According to research, children whose parents are actively involved in their education are more likely to graduate and pursue postsecondary education, have better grades and test scores, enrol in more advanced programs, attend class consistently, exhibit better behaviour, and have better social skills (Henderson and Mapp, 2012). In essence, parental participation in education can be viewed as a catalyst that ignites a child's drive and motivation to achieve both academically and personally.

The development of a child is not confined to the school environment alone. In fact, a great deal of learning happens at home and in everyday experiences. The distance between home and school is closed when parents actively participate in their kids' education, creating a more seamless and integrated learning experience for the child. Through such involvement, parents can share their values, beliefs, and aspirations with their children, which often shapes the students' perspectives on learning and their future ambitions. Beyond academic performance, parental participation plays a vital role in a child's psychological well-being. Eccles and Harold (1993) highlighted that children with engaged parents tend to have higher self-esteem and less depression, likely because these children feel a greater sense of family support and connection. Parental participation also fosters a more conducive environment for learning. When parents show interest in their child's education, they inadvertently reinforce the importance of school, creating a culture of respect and value for education. This culture often manifests in the child's attitude towards learning, leading to a higher level of intrinsic motivation (Grolnick & Slowiaczek, 1994).

Teachers too, benefit from increased parental participation. When parents and teachers form collaborative relationships, it provides opportunities for richer feedback about student progress and behavior. Such collaboration can lead to more tailored teaching strategies that cater for individual student needs, ultimately resulting in a more effective teaching process (Epstein, 2001). Furthermore, schools as entities benefit from parental participation. Engaged parents often volunteer, contribute to school events, and participate in school decision-making processes. This creates a more inclusive and collaborative school environment, fostering community spirit and strengthening the school's social fabric (Sanders and Lewis, 2005). From a societal perspective, parental participation has longer-term benefits. Engaged parents not only support their own children but also contribute to creating a generation of well-educated, well-adjusted adults. These individuals are more likely to participate actively in society, leading to more informed and cohesive communities (Coleman, 1988).

However, it's essential to acknowledge the diverse ways parents can be involved. Participation does not solely refer to attending parent-teacher conferences or volunteering at school events. It encompasses a broad spectrum of activities, including helping with homework, discussing school activities at home, encouraging reading, and setting academic expectations (Hill & Tyson, 2009). The depth and breadth of the impact of parental participation on children's education cannot be overstated. Its significance stretches beyond mere academic achievements to influence the social, psychological, and motivational facets of a child's life. Schools, communities, and, most importantly, students thrive when parents are actively engaged in the educational journey.

Parent Role

Every parents wants the best for their children. Thus explore strategies such as openness nurturing, caring, communication, acceptance and empathy, discipline, inculcate concept of right and wrong (Aloni & Ntorue, 2013) and ability to face challenges and character moulding at all times (Awake, 2011). The researcher synthesized that this wholesome conduct exhibited by parents not only add value to the child attitude, but triggers parents child relationship.

As the first social group, the family shapes the child's personality, his attitudes, needs and ways to meet them. It also contributes to the development of skills and abilities of the child, as well as by erecting requirements helps shape the needs and affects the level of educational attainment. The impact of parents is particularly important for the socio-moral and intellectual field of children development, including the achievement of school maturity. The family has great importance for the child's development processes, thereby achieving proper level of school maturity. It is a major factor shaping his attitudes toward school, work and social interactions. For instance, studies have indicated that factors such as family income and SES, quality of child care and certain aspects of parenting during early childhood are positively linked to early developmental outcomes and readiness for school. Jeynes (2013) in the research that examined multiple factors that affect school achievement of young children, he considered Parental participation.

We have defined parental participation as the motivated parental attitudes and behaviors towards the education of children and have noted how this has strong and clear associations with social and academic results for children. Apart from the conventional classroom activities, the current and more elaborate definitions of parental involvement include activities and communication at home and in the communities of the parents and their children (for example, supervision and control, communication of the parent-children about school, parents' visits to schools and other institutions in the community for learning) as well as the expectations that parents have about learning.

Parental Attitudes

The proper development of children requires the formation of two strategies: child rearing and controlling their actions based on their age and the possibilities of the child's development. Educational strategies that involve offering support, warmth, acceptance and encouragement to an explorative environment. On the other hand, control strategies are useful in preventing children from adopting the wrong way of social interaction. Parent schooling educational and controls strategies, underline them in the parental attitude (parenting style) conduct with a child. Amirabadi (2011) points out, parenting style is defined as parent's behaviors in two dimensions' parental responsiveness and parental demands. The kind of affection that parents have towards the child determines the attitude they have towards the child. This comprises a propensity to behave in a certain way towards him and

also to hold a certain view on the matter. It is also a tendency to respond in a certain way to a child. The parental attitude is a very powerful factor, it elicits a response in the child in form of normal or abnormal behavior. Parental attitude, like any other attitude, consists of three components: It is classified into three domains namely; cognitive, emotional motivational and behavioral. The knowledge and beliefs held by parents about the child refer to parental attitude, how to assess their emotional attitude towards him and aspirations and motivations of actions and ways of behaving towards the child. Thus, we can say that parental attitudes are a relatively fixed and consistent organization of beliefs, feelings and actions towards the child. The importance of parental attitudes is even greater because the kind of attitude is largely dependent on the quality of the fulfillment of the fundamental role of the parent which is raising a child.

However, however, there is a problem of defining the conceptualisation of Parental participation which has been defined in a number of ways (Harris & Goodall, 2007). Some researchers differentiate between school-based and home-based parental involvement. School-based involvement refers to interactions between parents and school staff, as well as activities at school that involve parents (Hill, 2011). In contrast, home-based involvement includes activities that parents engage in with their children at home (Hill, 2011). Additionally, other studies have explored a third type of parental involvement, unrelated to school activities, such as participation in sports, games, or visits to cinemas and museums, which also influence academic performance (Nord et al., 1997).

To address this research gap, Cabrera and Volling (2019) put forth a "Developmental Ecological Systems Framework for understanding parents and children's development." This approach defines parents as part of the systems that are characterized by interdependent and reciprocal relationships between and among caregivers and children and how these relationships develop and transform over time and in context (Cabrera, Volling & Barr, 2018).

Notwithstanding, the extent to which parents are involved in the learning process of their children is influenced by a number of factors. First and top most is poor family economic status. Many families face harsh economic crisis which form unmanageable stress disorders, thereby causing withdrawal from full and effective participation in child welfare and learning. Family income is a good predictor of children's education. Duke-Natrebo (2014) opines that family poverty is associated with poor intellectual development of children, when parents lack the emotional/psychological stability required for remaining committed to their children's wellbeing (created by socioeconomic pressures), an opening is created therein. Second, is Illiteracy/Educational Background. On International Education Day, President Bill Clinton said, "Literacy is a right and a responsibility; it is not a luxury." We must use all of our children's energy and ingenuity if we are to tackle the challenges of the twenty-first century. The role that parents play in their children's development is impacted by low levels of literacy and education.

In fact, Posse and Melgosa (2011) assert that illiterate parents are the major challenge in the cognitive development of the child. Bala (2001), in the study on implication of illiteracy and literacy of parents on the academic performance of primary pupils in Ilesa, Osun State, Nigeria: found that children whose parents have higher levels of education scored higher in their grades than parents whose parents had either little or no education. Poor educational background of parents may lead to poor communication between parents and their children. Third, is marital instability. Unstable homes subject the lives of many children to grave dangers. According to Duke-Natrebo (2014), children of parents who divorce often have inferior behavioural, cognitive, and health outcomes than children of stable homes. Parental divorce can cause significant upheaval in children's life, which may have some long-term effects, according to Amato's (2011) analysis. The lack of stability in the home can cause distractions enough to make parents fail or miss their parental obligations to their children.

Importance of Parental Participation

One complex area that has a big impact on pupils' academic achievement is parental involvement in their education. Numerous studies have demonstrated that active parental involvement in their children's education frequently results in favourable educational outcomes.

1. Higher Academic Achievement: It has been demonstrated that students often do better academically when their parents are actively involved in their education. Henderson and Mapp (2002) conducted an extensive review of 51 studies and found a consistent correlation

between parental involvement and student success, irrespective of the parent's race, class, or level of education. By setting expectations and valuing education, parents instill a sense of importance in schoolwork which motivates students to strive for excellence.

2. **Better Behavioral Outcomes:** Besides academic performance, parental participation can lead to positive behavioral outcomes. Sheldon and Epstein (2002) found that schools that foster strong connections with families and communities tend to experience fewer instances of student suspension, reported cases of violent behavior, and other disciplinary actions.
3. **Development of Positive Attitudes and Behaviors:** A more favourable attitude towards education is usually developed in children whose parents are actively involved in their education. In a meta-analysis, Jeynes (2007) found that parental participation is linked to increased student self-esteem and more favourable attitudes towards learning, and an increased number of academic credits earned.
4. **Enhanced Motivation and Aspiration:** Parents are essential in encouraging drive and ambition. Children's educational goals and drive to achieve can be significantly impacted by their parents' expectations, beliefs, and attitudes towards education. According to a study by Fan and Chen (2001), children whose parents are actively involved in their education are more likely to assume personal accountability for their education, which improves academic performance.
5. **Reduction in Dropout Rates:** Parental participation has also been linked with lower dropout rates. Rumberger (1995) suggests that students whose parents are engaged in their schooling are less likely to drop out compared to those with less involved parents. This is attributed to the supportive environment that these students have, which instills a sense of purpose and belonging.
6. **Improved School Climate:** When parents are actively involved in the educational process, schools as a whole can benefit. Epstein (2001) observed that schools with high levels of parental engagement often experience a more supportive and inclusive school climate, which can positively affect all students and not just those with active parents.
7. **More Effective Educators:** Teachers also benefit from parental participation. When parents and teachers collaborate, there's a better understanding of each child's unique needs, leading to tailored approaches to teaching. Hoover-Dempsey and Sandler (1997) argue that teacher efficacy improves as they receive more feedback and support from parents.
8. **Parental Understanding and Empathy:** Parents who are actively involved in their children's education gain a deeper understanding of the teaching process and the challenges teachers face. This understanding fosters a more empathetic approach to educators and often results in stronger teacher-parent relationships, as noted by Desforges and Abouchaar (2003).
9. **Social and Emotional Development:** Beyond the classroom, the involvement of parents can influence a child's social and emotional development. According to McWayne et al. (2004), children with involved parents tend to have better social skills, show improved emotional regulation, and are more equipped to form healthy relationships.
10. **Lifelong Value of Education:** Parental participation inculcates a lifelong value of education in children. This notion of valuing education does not just stop after high school but continues, fostering a culture of lifelong learning. Houtenville and Conway (2008) found that children of involved parents are more likely to pursue higher education and continue to value learning throughout their lives. The importance of parental participation in students' academic performance cannot be understated. From boosting academic achievements to fostering emotional and social development, active parental participation plays a pivotal role in molding successful students. While the level and nature of involvement might vary among families, its consistent positive impact is undeniable.

Benefits of Parental Participation

Parental involvement has a significant impact on children's education. According to Llamas and Tuazon (2016), parents are more comfortable participating in school-related activities when the educational system actively encourages their involvement. A strong partnership between parents and

schools can significantly enhance both academic outcomes and the school's overall performance. As a result, school administrators should actively promote parental engagement to support the school's mission and goals (Sapungan & Sapungan, 2014). Parental involvement in children's cognitive development is particularly valuable, as it boosts academic performance and helps children stay focused on their studies (Kwatubana & Makhalemele, 2015). This encourages the children not to easily lose interest when they fail to understand a certain topic and also will not absent himself from class for he knows that his parents would always track his attendance (Lemmer, 2017). Children of the involved parents are energetic and willing to attend classes, children learn punctuality at tender age, children learn to be persistent due to the constant checks on their progress by the parents. It is therefore important for such children to take responsibility of their work and be able to schedule their work and do it accordingly which is the aspect of organization (Sapungan & Sapungan, 2014). Through this parents can be able to ensure that their children excel in school (Hornby & Lafaele, 2011).

Labahn (1995) notes that parents are right to demand that children attend to their school work since there are children who are idle and will come up with all sorts of excuses in order not to do their work. Others are those which Lemmer (2007) has identified as comprising of improved self esteem, high level of school attendance and positive social demeanor. Sivertsen (2015) further points out that Parental participation is associated with positive behaviour, low rates of absenteeism and positive attitudes.

Some of the areas that have been identified in research to benefit from Parental participation are the developmental areas but also academic achievement. According to Hill and Craft (2003), social competence in children is closely related to higher Parental participation and Brody, et al., (1999) concluded that Parental participation enhances social skills and the child's ability to regulate his/her own behavior. Other cross-sectional and longitudinal studies also have confirmed that Parental participation is also linked to the improvement of language development and language skills that help children to succeed at school in early years of development (Domina, 2005). It has also been found that parents who are involved in their children's early childhood education results to higher reading and mathematics achievement, fewer absences and less behavioral concerns (Hiatt, 2001).

Parents also gain equally from the involvement in school since they are more informed on the education needs of their children, have positive relations and attitudes with teachers and ensure that their children get better education (Larocque, et al., 2011). Due to the fact that the pressure on parents to be held responsible for their children's performance at school has never been so high, schools and families must work together to understand that it takes both to make sure that every child will succeed (Hill & Taylor, 2004).

Parental Participation: A Panacea for Students Academic Performance.

Parental participation has long been acknowledged as a critical element in pupils' academic achievement. The importance of parents taking an active role in their kids' education goes far beyond just showing up to school functions. It entails being engaged with their child's academic journey at home, collaborating with educators, and creating an environment where learning is valued, nurtured, and celebrated. This active involvement, of course, can be likened to a panacea, a remedy to boost academic performance and holistic development in students.

The foundation for academic success is laid at home. When students feel supported by their parents in their academic endeavors, they often exhibit an increased sense of self-worth and motivation to excel. Henderson and Mapp (2012) noted that there's a consistent correlation between parental participation and student success, irrespective of socioeconomic, racial, or ethnic backgrounds. This involvement is believed to foster a positive view of education, where learning is perceived not as a chore but as a meaningful and rewarding endeavor. Parental participation also serves to bridge the often-present divide between the educational experiences at school and home. By integrating the two, children benefit from a holistic learning environment where they can connect classroom experiences with real-world contexts, thereby enhancing comprehension and retention (Eccles & Harold, 1993).

Additionally, the proactive involvement of parents in their child's education tends to instill a sense of responsibility in the student. Recognizing the investment and interest of their parents, students often

adopt a heightened sense of ownership over their learning outcomes. The accountability that emerges from this dynamic has been linked to improved study habits, higher levels of concentration, and an intrinsic motivation to learn (Flouri et. al, 2004).

Moreover, parents, being the primary influencers in their children's lives, play a significant role in molding their attitudes, beliefs, and aspirations. When parents demonstrate an appreciation for education and continuous learning, they inadvertently instill the same values in their children. Research by Fan and Chen (2001) found that students with involved parents tend to take personal responsibility for their learning, leading to better academic outcomes.

Beyond the immediate academic realm, parental participation significantly impacts students' psychological and emotional well-being. The supportive backdrop that engaged parents create fosters a strong sense of security in children, making them more resilient to academic challenges and less likely to succumb to stress and anxiety. Moreover, this consistent support has been linked to higher self-esteem, more positive attitudes toward school, and a decreased likelihood of behavioral problems (Hoover-Dempsey & Sandler, 1997).

Teachers, too, stand to benefit from increased parental participation. The insights and feedback from parents often provide educators with a more holistic understanding of the student, allowing for tailored teaching strategies that cater to individual needs. This collaborative relationship, as Epstein (2001) notes, results in a more effective teaching process, further bolstering student academic performance. From a broader societal perspective, the implications of parental involvement are far-reaching. Engaged parents often contribute positively to the school community, be it through volunteering, participating in school events, or decision-making processes. This involvement not only strengthens the school's fabric but also serves as a testament to the broader community about the value of education, potentially inspiring others to adopt a similar stance (Sanders & Lewis, 2005).

In essence, the myriad benefits of parental participation underscore its potential as a panacea for students' academic performance. While it may not be the sole determining factor, its role is undeniable and pivotal. For an education system striving for excellence and holistic development, parental participation emerges not merely as an added advantage but as an indispensable component.

Barriers of Parental Participation

Despite the fact that Parental involvement is considered to be very important to the educational performance of children, there are factors which hinders parents from participating in their children's learning process. Although there are still obstacles, federal policy has attempted to increase parental participation, particularly in urban, low-income, and disadvantaged regions (Smith et al., 2011). Poverty or socioeconomic situation, race/ethnicity and culture, language, parental education, and pragmatic factors are a few of these obstacles.

Parents from low SES and poverty stricken backgrounds are likely to have work schedules that do not permit participation, lack the materials and knowledge to participate, no transportation, and stress because they live in dangerous communities. Stressors which are associated with poverty include; financial difficulties and mental health problems which might lead to negative shift in the way parents view themselves and their capacity to parent will have an impact on their ability to participate when they are having difficulty supporting their family (Mayo & Siraj, 2015). Parents' mental health can be impacted by poverty, and as mental health influences parental involvement, parents may be more concerned with meeting their children's fundamental needs than with their intellectual performance in school (Hill & Taylor, 2004).

According to the literature, families from various or ethnic origins may have varying parent participation, but this is not often recognised; their views and perceptions of involvement may differ from those of the broader public (Lee & Bowen, 2006). Some of the scholars have suggested that socio cultural values and cultural narratives are a form of participation in some culturally/ethnically diverse families and that these families often employ strategies unknown to others and beneficial to their children's education. For instance, some minority families will consider as involvement, mentoring the children on how they should work and contribute to the needs of the family. This type of parent involvement may be the least visible and may not be well understood by the general population (Lopez, 2001). The language problem hampers the non-English speaking families in their

interaction with teachers and schools.

This barrier can be linked with low engagement in families but in reality, it might simply be that these families are swamped and daunted (La Rocque et al, 2011). Supporting the rights of translators and bilingual staff members can at least relieve the anger and aid in the process of integrating families and schools/teachers. This paper has also identified that parents' levels of education may hinder their participation in their children's achievement. Some parents may not have any importance in education because of their own background and experience in school (LaRocque et al, 2011). Or, parents may have had a bad experience at school themselves (Lee & Bowen, 2006). This can lead to truancy and such may be linked to students' reluctance to ask questions from teachers or schools because they feel that they are less privileged (Lareau, 1996). Factors which fall under the logistical barriers include; Parents cannot change their working time to be able to attend the meetings. Families are financially paralyzed by their jobs and their health insurance and other benefits, which they cannot afford to lose; hence they cannot afford to take time off work for fear of losing their jobs (LaRocque et al., 2011).

There may also be employment barriers which may hinder their participation making it difficult for them to be involved during school time and hence have low participation than those with stable wage employment (LaRocque et al, 2011). Consequently, parents who are physically and legally present at school but are unable to attend various events or are less visibly engaged may be perceived as uncaring or uninvolved, leading to negative judgments about both the parents and their children (Lee & Bowen, 2006). Hill and Craft (2003) observed that teachers often associate school-level parental involvement with a high regard for education, while the opposite conclusion can be drawn about parents who cannot attend school meetings or give their time for volunteering.

CONCLUSION

This study examined parental participation as a panacea for raising the academic achievement of Rivers State secondary school pupils. According to the study, pupils' performance is significantly impacted by parents' involvement in their education. There was also widespread belief that a student's performance is determined by how involved their parents are in their education.

SUGGESTIONS

Based on the foregoing discussion, the following suggestions were made:

1. **Monitoring/Evaluation:** Parents should embark on intensive monitoring as well evaluation to ascertain students' performance outcomes. This will not only assists parents to identify or know of students weakness, but be of help to either teach or look out for experts to bridge the gap, especially in subject area where they seems to be very weak.
2. **Provision of Pleasant Study Atmosphere:** Conducive environment remains the hallmark for effective learning. Therefore, parents especially those whose children are day students should painstakingly create conducive atmosphere free from distraction.
3. **Participation in Extra-Academic Programmes:** Parents as well teachers should at all times encourage students' to participate or take part in extra-academic programmes such as; inter school debate, quiz competition, learning with colleagues, being involved in seminar and conferences and extra-moral class etc. This will not only boost their morale, but skills, knowledge and ability.
4. **Motivation:** Parents should reward their children for good academic performance such as; recognition, praise, given of prizes and announcing it to other persons. This also will enhance student's commitment to study.
5. **Sound Parents/Teachers Communication Network:** A sound communication platform should be established between parents and teachers in order to help check and mitigate student's unwholesome conduct that hinders effective learning.
6. **Parents School Management Meeting:** Periodic and timely scheduling of parents teachers forum (PTF) should be encouraged by parents and the school authority, and decision bordering on students' performance be discussed and implemented to the brim.
7. **Parents should be their children's advocate** by taking an active part and interest in what their child learns at schools.

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